

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Sudaryono, Azis, Y., & Zulkifli. (2024). Talent Management, Leadership, and Organizational Culture: How Quality of Service Influences Excellent Service at Indonesia's Bhayangkara Hospital. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 7(2), 24-34.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.07.02.573

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Talent Management, Leadership, and Organizational Culture: How Quality of Service Influences Excellent Service at Indonesia's Bhayangkara Hospital

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to examine and develop excellent service at Bhayangkara Hospital by improving talent management, leadership, and organizational culture through service quality. This study employed an associative quantitative approach using a sample of 358 employees from 11 Bhayangkara Type B hospitals drawn from a population of 3452 using the Slovin formula. The data was analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) with the LISREL Version 10.20 application. The findings of this study reveal that key factors such as talent management, leadership, and organizational culture have a positive and significant effect on excellent service through partial quality of service. Based on this, we conclude that talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and service quality all have a positive effect on providing excellent medical services at Bhayangkara Hospital. Thus, we suggest practical implications such as investment in talent management, effective leadership, and positive organizational culture to improve the quality of service in hospitals.

Keywords: Talent Management, Leadership, Organizational Culture, Excellent Service, Quality of Service

1. Introduction

The goal of health sector development is to increase the community's access, quality, and equity of health services (Oliver, & Mossialos, 2004). The primary goal of health sector development is to promote public health by making health services more accessible, egalitarian, and inexpensive to both urban and rural communities. In this framework, hospitals play an important role as institutions that provide comprehensive individual health care through inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services. Health development in hospitals strives to establish a society that values healthy behavior, which includes awareness, desire, and the ability to live a healthy life and have access to quality health services in order to live in a healthier environment.

Regulations in Indonesia categorize hospitals based on their service capabilities, health facilities, supporting facilities, and human resources. Hospital rankings are divided into Class A, Class B, Class C, and Class D. The

largest number of hospitals (RS) in Indonesia according to class is type C at 1,593 (52.4%), then class D and D Pratama at 905 (29.8%), class B at 437 hospitals (14.4%), and class A at 60 (2.0%), while the remaining 47 (1.5%) were hospitals in categories whose class had not been determined (47 RS). Hospitals registered with the Ministry of Health are operated by various agencies or institutions, including the central government, regional government, police, and national army, as well as state-owned and private enterprises. In 2021, 36 hospitals will be organized by the Ministry of Health (1.2%), 63 hospitals from other ministries and state-owned enterprises (2.1%), 168 hospitals (5.5%) organized by the National Army/Police, and 847 hospitals (27.8%), by Regional Government, while the private sector operates the largest number of hospitals with 1,928 hospitals (63.4%).

As a health service institution, hospitals must pay attention to quality and patient safety (Grabau, 2018). Fulfilling the quality of service in hospitals is carried out in two ways: by improving quality internally and externally. Internal quality is carried out periodically every month through the establishment, assessment, and reporting of national and external quality standards, namely through hospital accreditation surveys by the Independent Accreditation Organizing Institution. According to Law No. 44 of 2009 concerning Hospitals, "hospitals are obliged to improve the quality of service, which is evaluated periodically, at least once every 3 years, and is guided by applicable standards.

Quality of service involves meeting patient needs holistically, including physical, emotional, and psychological aspects. Besides Quality of Service, there is the Excellent Service concept which emphasizes the importance of understanding and responding to patient needs as a whole to provide the most positive experience (Sari, Kartikasari & Ulfah, 2021). Quality of service and excellent service are closely related because excellent service is the result of efforts to achieve optimal quality of service. In the context of health services, excellent service refers to the highest standards in providing services to patients or customers (Sumarni & Gunawan, 2022). In contrast, quality of service involves all aspects of the delivery of care or services that meet patient expectations and needs.

Bhayangkara Hospital is one of the hospitals that provide services in the form of inpatient health services, 24-hour emergency room, laboratory, radiology, outpatient health services, medical supporting health services, medical check-up, integrated service center, prisoner health services, *visum et repertum* and autopsy, and drug services. The number of Bhayangkara Hospitals based on type throughout Indonesia is 58 hospitals, 1 Bhayangkara Hospital with type A, 11 Bhayangkara Hospitals with type B, 27 Bhayangkara Hospitals with type C, and 18 Bhayangkara Hospitals with type D. Bhayangkara Hospital tasked with carrying out Police Medical service activities to support the operational duties of the National Police and Police Health Services for Civil Servants at the National Police and their families as well as the general public in an excellent manner.

Based on the recap of the 2022 National Bhayangkara Type B Hospital Quality Indicator data collection, almost all Bhayangkara Type B Hospitals have met national standards. However, there are still four Bhayangkara Type B Hospitals (Bhayangkara Hospital Jambi, Bhayangkara Hospital Jayapura, Bhayangkara Hospital Setukpa Polri and Bhayangkara Balikpapan Hospital) which do not comply with national standards. This is because the systems and processes in the hospital are less than optimal to achieve the expected level of compliance. This can also be caused by problems in time management, coordination, and communication, and a lack of awareness or commitment to the importance of complying with quality standards can result in low levels of compliance. This can be seen in the results of observations regarding several problems faced by the four Bhayangkara hospitals which do not meet national standards, such as complaints regarding the lack of communication skills of health workers, poor service to patients, poor sanitation and hygiene aspects, delays in treatment and drug services, and so on. which shows that several Bhayangkara Type B Hospitals have not yet complied with quality standards.

Referring to the aforementioned phenomenon, this study was carried out in response to the 2022 Bhayangkara Type B Hospital National Quality Indicator data, which shows that numerous hospitals still fail to fulfill national criteria. The goal of this research is to identify the reasons that may be causing such disparities. Talent management, leadership, and organizational culture are some of the elements that might have an impact on providing outstanding service in hospitals. By understanding these factors, it is hoped that researchers can provide insight into improving systems and practices at Bhayangkara Hospital so that they can increase the level of compliance with national quality standards.

It is hoped that the results of this research will be useful for developing theories regarding talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and excellent service through quality of service. Apart from that, it can be used as input or reference material and studied for the development of theory and knowledge in the field of human resource management, especially regarding talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and excellent service through quality of service. Practically, this research is expected to be used as input or benchmark as well as consideration for company leaders to adopt policies related to talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and excellent service through quality of service.

To show that there is novelty between this research and research that has been carried out previously, the researchers attempted to compare the various variables, research methods, and results of research that has been carried out regarding the excellent service of Bhayangkara Polri Hospital by strengthening talent management, leadership, and organizational culture through hospital quality of service. The novelty of this research is that it combines key factors, namely talent management, leadership, and organizational culture, as elements that are considered to influence the quality of service in hospitals. This approach has never been used before in the context of the Bhayangkara Polri Hospital or perhaps has never been used holistically in similar research at other hospitals. This research is novel in its specific context, namely, excellent service at Bhayangkara Hospital.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author (2023)

The variables are divided into two, namely dependent variables and independent variables. According to De Nisi (2000), to achieve excellent service, organizations need to ensure that they have high-quality individuals in important positions. Talent management plays a role in ensuring that organizations can recruit, develop, and retain individuals with high ability and potential to provide excellent service. Regarding leadership variables, the results of research conducted by Faidi et al. (2020) show that good visionary leadership has an impact on excellent service, in line with the hypothesis of this research. Likewise, the research results of Dwi and Joko (2017), that there is a positive and significant influence of organizational culture on excellent service quality. Dewiana's findings also concluded that in 2022, excellent service will have a positive and significant effect on quality service. These three independent variables (talent management, leadership, and organizational culture) also influence service quality (Khalood, and Nor, 2023). This is what underlies the researcher's hypothesis, as follows:

- H1: It is suspected that Talent Management influences excellent service
- H2: It is suspected that leadership influences excellent service
- H3: It is suspected that organizational culture influences excellent service
- H4: It is suspected that quality of service influences excellent service
- H5: It is suspected that Talent Management influences quality of service
- H6: It is suspected that leadership influences the quality of service
- H7: It is suspected that organizational culture influences the quality of service

2. Method

2.1. Data Collection

Based on the problem and objectives, this research uses a type of quantitative research that attempts to explain the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing. In this case, it explains whether there is an influence from the excellent service of the Bhayangkara Polri Hospital by strengthening talent management, leadership, and organizational culture through the hospital's quality of service. This research applies associative research methods, which aim to determine the relationship between two or more variables. The population used in this study was 3,452 employees from 11 Bhayangkara Type B hospitals. The reason for choosing Bhayangkara Type B Hospital was based on its potential to make a significant contribution to the development of science and the improvement of health services. To calculate the determination of sample size, the Slovin formula is used.

$$n = \frac{N}{N.(d^2) + 1}$$

With this technique, a sample of 358 respondents was taken. The process of selecting and collecting samples was carried out using the proportional stratified random sampling method. Following the approach and research methods used, this research has two types of data, consisting of primary data and secondary data. There are several methods used, namely observation, document study, and questionnaires. The type of questionnaire used in this research is a closed questionnaire. This research also uses a questionnaire with a Likert scale to measure the respondent's level of agreement with the statements stated in the questionnaire. The research instrument provides alternative answers to each question, and respondents can choose 1 to 5, which are provided with alternative answers chosen for each statement. The Likert scale consists of five scales: strongly agree (SA), agree (A), somewhat agree (SMA), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD).

Table 2: Variable Operation

Variable	Dimension	Indicators	Question Items
Talent Management (X1)	1. Talent Attraction	• Social Domain	1
		• Organizational Excellence	2
	2. Talent Development	• Performance Management	3
		• Talent Training	4
		• Leadership Development	5
	3. Talent Retention	• comparison	6
		• Job Satisfaction	7
		• Non-financial Reward	8
		• Employee empowerment	9
			• employee motivation
Leadership (X2)	1. briefing/instruction	• Giving a clear instruction	1
		• encourage initiatives	2
		• Communicate the Vision	3
	2. Communication	• openness	4
		• Empathy	5
	3. Decision Making	• Information Analysis	6
		• Courage to Take Risk	7
	4. Motivating	• Giving Appreciation	8
		Positive encouragement	9
		Creating positive environment	10
Organizational	1. Innovative in	• creating new ideas	1

Culture (X3)	calculating risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • courage to take risks in developing new ideas 	2
	2. result oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • target setting 	3
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of the results of the work done 	4
	3. Oriented to all employee interests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Met the need to finish the task 	5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting the achievement of the employee 		6	
Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Question items
	4. Detail oriented on tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • careful 	7
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy of work 	8
Excellent service (Y)	1. Efficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource utilization 	1
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured work processes 	2
	2. Effective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Result achievement 	3
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Quality 	4
	3. Clear	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication 	5
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of information 	6
	4. Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource utilization 	7
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget management and expenditure 	8
	5. Certainty of time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fulfillment of schedules 	9
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of tasks on time 	10
	6. Accuracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accurate and precise data or information 	11
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate action according to protocol or applicable procedures 	12
	7. Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk prevention 	13
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of security standards 	14
	8. Fair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equal treatment 	15
	9. Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform duty 	16
	10. Comprehensive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive and detailed information, documentation or actions 	17
	11. Professional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical attitude and respect for professional ethics 	18
Quality of service (Z)	1. National Hospital Quality Indicators (INM-RS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hand Hygiene Compliance 	1
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with the Use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) 	2

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance Patient identification 	3
Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Question items
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency Cesarean Section Response Time 	4
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outpatient Waiting Times 	5
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Postponement of Elective Surgery 	6
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adherence to doctor visit times 	7
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting Critical Laboratory Results 	8
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with the use of the National Formulary 	9
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adherence to the Clinical Pathway Flow 	10
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with efforts to prevent the risk of patient falls 	11
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complaint Time Response Speed 	12
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Satisfaction 	13
	2. Hospital Priority Quality Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Identification Compliance 	14
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hand Hygiene Compliance 	15
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with efforts to prevent the risk of patient falls 	16
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of running water 24 hours 	17
	3. Unit Priority Quality Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Satisfaction Survey 	18
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting of Critical Laboratory results 	19

2.2 Data Analysis

The data analysis technique in this research uses the structural equation model (SEM) with the LISREL 10.20 program. Data analysis using a confirmatory strategy with a two-step approach, namely the measurement model-2nd CFA test and the hybrid structural model test. This path analysis model uses the following model and structural equations:

Figure 2: Schematic Model of Relationships Between Variables

Source: Author (2023)

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Variable Analysis

The data obtained in this research was in the form of distributing questionnaires to employees of Bhayangkara Type B Hospital, with a total sample of 358 respondents. In total, the three indicators used to measure the talent management variable produced a respondent answer of 4.06; this value, when referring to the interval scale, falls into the 3.40–4.19 category, meaning that overall talent management (X1) at 11 Bhayangkara Type B hospitals falls into the good category.

In total, the four indicators used to measure the leadership variable (X2) produced a respondent answer of 4.08; this value, when referring to the interval scale, falls into the category 3.40–110.19, meaning that overall leadership at 11 Bhayangkara Type B hospitals is in the category Good.

In total, eight indicators used to measure the organizational culture variable (X3) produced a respondent answer of 4.07; this value, when referring to the interval scale, falls into the category 3.40–4.19, meaning that overall organizational culture at 11 Bhayangkara Type B hospitals falls into the good category.

.In total, eleven indicators used to measure the excellent service (Y) variable produced a respondent answer of 4.07; this value, when referring to the interval scale, falls into the 3.40–4.19 category, meaning overall excellent service at 11 Bhayangkara Type B hospitals falls into the good category.

In total, the four indicators used to measure the Quality of Service (Z) variable produced a respondent answer of 3.91. This value, when referring to the interval scale, is in the 122 categories, 2.50–3.24, meaning that the overall quality of service at 11 Bhayangkara hospitals, Type B, is in a good category.

3.2 Validity and Reliability Test

The validity and reliability results in the SEM model in the Lisrel program version 10.20 were obtained from the first stage, namely confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). In this first stage, the observed variables or indicators for each latent variable must first meet the validity and reliability requirements. After all the tests meet the requirements, the second stage is carried out, namely the second-order CFA (2ndCFA) from Lisrel 10.20 processing. The results obtained are in the form of a path diagram and printed output. The variables talent management, leadership, and organizational culture were then tested on the instrument with a significance level of 0.05 using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO-MSA) factor analysis and obtained a KMO value of $0.947 \geq 0.05$ and a loading factor value for each statement greater than 0.4. So it can be said that

all leadership statements can be continued for further analysis. Based on the results of standardized estimates of the variables talent management, leadership, and organizational culture, all indicators have loading factors above 0.60, which shows that these indicators are valid for measuring the construct.

3.3 Structural Model Result (T-value)

Figure 3: Structural Model Result T-value

Source: Author, (2023)

3.4 Hypothesis testing

After the goodness of fit criteria are met for the estimated structural model, then analysis of the model's structural relationships (hypothesis testing) can be carried out.

Table 3.1: Structural Equation

Path	Standardized path estimate	t-value	t-table
TALMEN - EXSER	0.15	5.04	> 1.96
LEADER - EXSER	0.23	2.28	> 1.96
CULTUR - EXSER	0.24	2.35	> 1.96
TALMEN - QOS	0.10	7.32	> 1.96
LEADER - QOS	0.15	2.46	> 1.96
CULTUR - QOS	0.16	2.06	> 1.96
EXSER - QOS	0.65	10.39	> 1.96

Source: Processed Data, 2023

Table 3.2: Variance explained

Variance explained for endogenous variable	R ²
EXSER	0.394
QOS	0.483

Source: Processed Data, 2023

After assessing the model as a whole and testing the construct relationships as hypothesized, the next step is to discuss the research results as follows:

- 1) The influence of talent management on excellent service obtained a t-value of $5.04 > 1.96$. The anticipated positive Talent Management to Excellent Service coefficient value shows 0.15. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the talent management variable has a positive and significant effect on the excellent service variable.
- 2) The influence of leadership on excellent service obtained a t-value of $2.28 > 1.96$. The anticipated positive Leadership to Excellent Service coefficient value shows 0.23. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H2 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent Service variable.
- 3) The influence of organizational culture on excellent service obtained a t-value of $2.35 > 1.96$. The positive anticipated Organizational Culture to Excellent Service coefficient value shows 0.24. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H3 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the Organizational Culture variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent Service variable.
- 4) The influence of quality of service on excellent service. The anticipated positive Quality of Service to Excellent Service coefficient value shows 0.65. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H4 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the Quality of Service variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent Service variable.
- 5) The influence of talent management on quality of service. Based on Table 3.1, the t-value is $7.32 > 1.96$. The anticipated positive Talent Management to Quality of Service coefficient value shows 0.10. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H5 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the Talent Management variable has a positive and significant effect on the Quality of Service variable.
- 6) The influence of leadership on quality of service. Based on Table 3.1, the t-value is $2.46 > 1.96$. The anticipated positive Leadership to Quality of Service coefficient value shows 0.15. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H6 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on the Quality of Service variable.
- 7) The influence of organizational culture on quality of service. Based on Table 3.1, the t-value is $2.35 > 1.96$. The positive anticipated Organizational Culture to Quality of Service coefficient value shows 0.16. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. Based on these results, it shows that H7 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that the Organizational Culture variable has a positive and significant effect on the Quality of Service variable.

4. Discussion

4.1 *The Influence of Talent Management, Leadership, and Organizational Culture on Excellent Service*

The Talent Management variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent Service variable. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with the theory that Talent Management is a concept related to human resource management that aims to develop employees and retain them in the long term (Donald, 2014).

The Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent service variable. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with previous research by Faidi., et, al, (2020) that the influence of good visionary leadership has an impact on excellent service. This research is in accordance with the theory that the leadership philosophy of the past has the potential to be developed professionally in the present (Priest & Seemiller, 2018).

The Organizational Culture variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent Service variable. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with the theory put forward by Robbins that the function of the existence of an organization is to increase mutual commitment (Wardiah, 2016). This is also in accordance with Rahmayanty's statement that in providing excellent service it is necessary to pay attention to providing motivation and encouragement as well as providing education and training to improve employee quality, paying attention to employee welfare as well as monitoring and controlling the system (Dewi & Hariyati, 2017).

The Quality of Service variable has a positive and significant effect on the Excellent Service variable. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with previous research by Novitasari (2022) which concluded that Excellent Service has a positive and significant effect on Quality Service.

The novelty of this research provides a new contribution to the field of health services, especially at the Bhayangkara Polri Hospital. This research shows that quality of service has a positive and significant influence on excellent service, which is an indicator of a hospital's success in providing quality health services. This research also reveals the factors that influence the quality of service and excellent service and provides recommendations for improving both.

4.2 The Influence of Talent Management, Leadership, and Organizational Culture on Quality Service

The Talent Management variable has a positive and significant effect on the Quality of Service variable. It is proven that the t-value is $7.32 > 1.96$. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with previous research by Khalood and Nor (2023), in accordance with the theory put forward by Groves in Hermin (2013) Talent Management is generally related to training on development strategies, identifying talent gaps, succession planning, as well as recruiting, selecting, educating, motivating and nurturing talented employees through various initiatives.

The Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on the Quality of Service variable. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with previous researchers, Darwin (2020), that leadership influences the quality of service. This research is in accordance with the theory put forward by Asmuji (2013) that quality leadership can be said to be the main source of good and bad quality nursing service through the implementation of an effective quality management system.

The Organizational Culture variable has a positive and significant effect on the Quality of Service variable. This condition can be interpreted as meaning that a positive coefficient value encourages a significant and strong influence between the two variables above. This research is in accordance with previous researcher Radito Soesanto (2023) who stated that organizational culture influences the quality of service. This research is in accordance with the theory put forward by Osborne and Plastrik (2000) The attitudes and behaviors that emerge in an organization describe the organization's culture.

Based on the research results and overall discussion, it is concluded that talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and quality of service have a positive and significant influence on excellent service at

Bhayangkara Hospital. Talent management, servant leadership, and a strong organizational culture can improve service quality and employee satisfaction, while improving the quality of service also contributes to achieving excellent service. Strategies involving employee development and talent management, along with quality leadership and a positive organizational culture, have a positive impact on the quality of service at the hospital. The results of this research provide a clear picture of the importance of factors such as talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and quality of service in improving excellent service at Bhayangkara Hospital. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the Bhayangkara Polri Hospital will gain great benefits by optimizing the implementation of talent management, leadership, organizational culture, and quality of service. Implementation of strategies that focus on talent management, servant leadership, a positive organizational culture, and improving the quality of service will contribute positively to achieving excellent service at the hospital. Improved service quality and employee satisfaction, together with improvements in quality of service, would be outcomes that can be expected from the holistic application of these factors.

Author Contributions: Each authors contributed to this research.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics approval: Not applicable.

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